

Generative AI in Diamond Open Access Publishing

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Introduction

Generative artificial intelligence (AI) has brought many opportunities and challenges to scholarly publishing. While it can help streamline editorial workflows, reduce repetitive tasks and improve metadata, it also raises serious questions around research integrity, authorship, copyright, bias and protection of confidential information.

Familiarity with AI tools and their implications enables Diamond OA journals to:

- make informed choices about whether and how to use AI in publishing workflows,
- protect against integrity breaches such as fabricated data or ghost authorship,
- define policies governing the use of AI in submitted manuscripts, the peer review process, and production workflows,
- maintain community trust while keeping pace with global publishing standards.

This selection of open access and free-to-read resources is designed to help Diamond OA journals to build practical knowledge, policies, and skills necessary to deal with challenges associated with the use of AI. It was initiated within the No-Fee Open Access Publishing in Africa Community of Practice and is a result of the [Collaboration for sustainable open access publishing in Africa](#) project, supported by the Wellcome Trust [grant number 228148/Z/23/Z].

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Introduction to Generative AI in Publishing

Resources in this section explain what generative AI tools are and why they matter for scholarly publishing. AI tools can assist with language editing, summaries, and metadata, but they also involve risks of errors, bias and fabricated content. For Diamond OA journals, understanding both the opportunities and the risks is essential to safeguard integrity, make informed choices, and maintain trust.

Topics

- Core concepts of AI, generative AI and LLMs
- AI applications in scholarly publishing
- Main limitations (hallucinations, bias, lack of transparency)
- AI literacy in scholarly publishing

Resources

Guides

- 'AI Basics'. MIT Sloan Teaching & Learning Technologies. URL: <https://mitsloanedtech.mit.edu/ai/basics/>
- Naseem, Carah, Omorodion Okuonghae, and Nosakhare Okuonghae. 2025. 'Uses of AI in Scholarly Publishing'. Paper presented at 47th SSP Annual Meeting. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.14293/S2199-SSP-AM25-01012>.

Online courses

- 'A Free Online Introduction to Artificial Intelligence for Non-Experts'. Elements of AI. University of Helsinki & MIInnaLearn. URL: <https://www.elementsofai.com/>
- 'An Introduction to Artificial Intelligence'. Open Learning. URL: <https://www.open.edu/openlearn/education-development/ai-matters/content-section-overview>
- 'AI vs. Generative AI: Exploring the Artificial Intelligence Landscape.' Coursera. 2024. URL: <https://www.coursera.org/articles/ai-vs-generative-ai>

Publications and blogs

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- Lieberum, Judith-Lisa, Markus Toews, Maria-Inti Metzendorf, et al. 2025. 'Large Language Models for Conducting Systematic Reviews: On the Rise, but Not yet Ready for Use—a Scoping Review.' *Journal of Clinical Epidemiology* 181: 111746. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclinepi.2025.111746>
- Salani, Justin, and Mass Masona Tapfuma. 2025. 'Artificial Intelligence Transforming the Publishing Industry: A Case of the Book Sector in Africa.' *Frontiers in Research Metrics and Analytics*. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.3389/frma.2025.1504415>

Videos and webinars

- 'How Large Language Models Work.' IBM Technology, 2023.
URL: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=5sLYAQS9sWQ>
- Henrik Kniberg, 2024. 'Generative AI in a Nutshell - How to Survive and Thrive in the Age of AI.' (German, Ukrainian).
URL: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=2IK3DFHRFfw>
- 'GPT, Language Models, and AI in Scholarly Publishing.' European Association of Science Editors (EASE). 2023.
URL: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=WiPWaXrHpOI>
- 'The Influence of AI on Academic Publishing.' NTU Library. 2024.
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- 'The Impact of Artificial Intelligence (AI) on Scholarly Writing and Publishing.' Academy of Science of South Africa. 2023.
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- 'Webinar: AI and Academic Publishing - What Does the Future Hold?' Scientific Advice Mechanism. 2024. URL: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=uXiWR54pQ28>
- 'How AI Is Changing Research and Publishing (Part 1).' Research4Life. 2025. URL: https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=-X7qZRpW_Pc.
- 'Decolonising AI.' Africa Social Work & Development Network ASWDNet. 2024. URL: <https://youtu.be/IRxxWNQiEUg?si=k08umcFnZUMPL3C>

Research integrity

Resources in this section help journal editors understand how the use of generative AI can influence research integrity, highlighting key risks such as fabrication, falsification, authorship disputes, plagiarism, copyright concerns, and bias in AI-generated content. Editors will also find guidance on protecting confidentiality and privacy and the responsible and informed use of AI-detection tools.

Topics outline

- AI assistance in writing
- Risks: fabrication, falsification, authorship issues, plagiarism, copyright issues, bias (e.g. in training data and outputs)
- Confidentiality and privacy risks
- AI in manuscript screening (detecting plagiarism, image manipulation, and data issues): tools, limits and responsible use

Resources

Recommendations and guides

- Generative AI in Scholarly Communications. STM. 2023. URL: <https://stm-assoc.org/document/stm-generative-ai-paper-2023/>

Publications and blogs

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- 'AI as Unintentional Co-Author: Risks Ethics | Responsible AI.' Enago. URL: <https://www.enago.com/responsible-ai-movement/resources/ai-unintentional-co-author-ethical-risks>
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- Hutson, James. 2024. 'Rethinking Plagiarism in the Era of Generative AI.' *Journal of Intelligent Communication* 3 (2): 20–31. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.54963/jic.v3i2.220>.
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Videos and webinars

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- 'Artificial Intelligence and Scholarly Publications: Expectations, Equity and Ethics.' American Society for Microbiology. 2024. URL: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=WvH3Wy3EZDk>
- 'SciELO South Africa – SciELO 25 Seminar: AI Detection Tools and Editorial Decision-Making Policies.' SciELO. 2023. URL: https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=Uj8_RZV8WII
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Use cases

- 'Reviewer Suspects Use of AI by an Author.' COPE: Committee on Publication Ethics. 2025. URL: <https://publicationethics.org/guidance/case/reviewer-suspects-use-ai-author>
- 'Handling an Article Produced by AI.' COPE: Committee on Publication Ethics. 2025. URL: <https://publicationethics.org/guidance/case/handling-article-produced-ai>.
- 'How Can We Defend against AI-Generated Articles Being Used as a Denial of Service Attack?' COPE: Committee on Publication Ethics. 2024. URL: <https://publicationethics.org/guidance/case/defend-against-ai-denial-service-attack>.
- 'How to Exclude Articles Generated by Artificial Intelligence.' COPE: Committee on Publication Ethics. 2024. URL: <https://publicationethics.org/guidance/case/how-exclude-articles-generated-artificial-intelligence>.

Peer review

Resources in this section explore the opportunities and risks of using artificial intelligence in peer review, highlighting both its potential benefits and associated risks. Editors will also find guidance on maintaining confidentiality and addressing the ethical implications of AI use in the peer review process.

Topics

- Algorithm-driven reviewer selection
- AI-assisted review reports
- Confidentiality
- Ethical issues

Resources

Recommendations and guides

- 'Generative AI in Scholarly Communications.' STM. 2023. URL: <https://stm-assoc.org/document/stm-generative-ai-paper-2023/>
- 'Recommendations on the Use of AI in Scholarly Communication.' EASE, 2024. URL: <https://ease.org.uk/2024/09/recommendations-on-the-use-of-ai-in-scholarly-communication/>

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Videos and webinars

- 'Artificial Intelligence (AI) and Peer Review.' COPE (Committee on Publication Ethics). 2023. URL: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=HJYB1laS598>
- 'Peer Review Across Borders and Technologies: Localizing the EASE Toolkit in the AI Era.' European Association of Science Editors (EASE). 2025. URL: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=2quicRY4w-E>
- 'How Peer Reviewers Are Using AI Tools in Scholarly Publishing.' HighWire. 2025. URL: <https://www.highwirepress.com/videos/understanding-how-peer-reviewers-use-ai-tools>
- 'Understanding How Peer Reviewers Use AI Tools.' HighWire Press, 2025. URL: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=RDCi5sEXMvw>.
- 'How AI Is Changing Research and Publishing (Part 2).' Research4Life. URL: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=hrZJI-luYY8>

Legal and ethical issues

Resources in this section help journals understand and manage risks associated with AI use in publishing, especially those associated with copyright, confidentiality and data protection, and vendor agreements.

Topics

- Copyright and ownership of AI-generated content
- Data protection requirements
- Vendor contracts: data use, security, etc.

Resources

Recommendations and guides

- 'Guidance on Generative AI, Strengthening Data Protection in a Rapidly Changing Digital Era.' European Data Protection Supervisor. 2025. URL: https://www.edps.europa.eu/data-protection/our-work/publications/guidelines/2025-10-28-guidance-generative-ai-strengthening-data-protection-rapidly-changing-digital-era_en

Publications and blogs

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Videos and webinars

- 'Research and Publishing Ethics in the Age of AI: Copyright, Community Consensus, and Spaces Between.' MSU Research, 2024.
URL: https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=Knh55PeB__Q
- 'How AI Is Changing Research and Publishing (Part 2).' Research4Life.
URL: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=hrZJI-luYY8>

Using AI in editorial tasks and production

Resources in this section provide a practical overview of how AI can support editorial workflows, from manuscript handling and peer review to copyediting and production. Emphasis is placed on responsible use, ethical considerations, and maintaining editorial standards.

Topics

- Key areas of the editorial workflow where AI tools can provide support
- Safe and unsafe uses of AI in editorial tasks
- Metadata generation and enrichment
- Language editing
- Plain-language summaries
- Automating workflows (e.g. email templates)

Resources

Recommendations and guides

- 'Generative AI in Scholarly Communications.' STM. 2023. URL: <https://stm-assoc.org/document/stm-generative-ai-paper-2023/>.
- 'Recommendations on the Use of AI in Scholarly Communication.' EASE, 2024. URL: <https://ease.org.uk/2024/09/recommendations-on-the-use-of-ai-in-scholarly-communication/>

Publications and blogs

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Videos and webinars

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- 'Navigating Academic Publishing with AI: Content Preparation, Solutions and Dissemination.' NTU Library, 2024. URL: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=yD2HsOkpmuw>
- 'Experiments in AI-Created Metadata.' Open Library Foundation. 2023. URL: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=i4PFApt4Mo8>
- 'How AI Can Streamline the Plain Language Summaries.' TrialAssure. 2023. URL: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=mbNDvVXgwMM>
- 'Practical Uses of AI and ML in the Scholarly Publishing Process (Best Practices Webinar Series).' HighWire Press, 2023. URL: https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=lkvIS_y5ysU

- 'Panel Session: A Steady Takeover: Exploring the Impact of AI on Academic Publishing.' OASPA Open Access Scholarly Publishing Association. 2023. URL: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=dq1FzLV7ChU>
- 'Editorial Governance and the Use of AI in African Scholarly Publishing.' HUMA. 2025. URL: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=LCz0s96wnLI>

Addressing AI use in journal policies

This section provides key resources for developing or updating policies on the ethical and transparent use of AI in scholarly publishing, highlighting in particular disclosure requirements, permitted and prohibited uses of AI, confidentiality considerations, and recommended practices.

Topics

- Disclosure
- Permitted/prohibited uses,
- Confidentiality

Resources

Recommendations and guides

- 'Generative AI in Scholarly Communications.' STM. 2023. URL: <https://stm-assoc.org/document/stm-generative-ai-paper-2023/>.
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Videos and webinars

- 'Emerging AI Dilemmas in Scholarly Publishing.' COPE: Committee on Publication Ethics. URL: <https://publicationethics.org/topic-discussions/emerging-ai-dilemmas-scholarly-publishing>
- 'Artificial Intelligence and Scholarly Publications: Expectations, Equity and Ethics.' American Society for Microbiology, 2024. URL: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=WvH3WY3EZDk>

Examples

- 'Editorial Policies.' South African Journal of Science. 2025. URL: <https://sajs.co.za/editorial-policies#AI-LMMs>
- 'Research Guides: Artificial Intelligence (AI): Publisher Policies. Purdue University Libraries.' URL: <https://guides.lib.purdue.edu/c.php?g=1371380&p=10135076>